
SEROPREVALENCE OF VARICELLA-ZOSTER VIRUS INFECTION AMONG PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN IN KADUNA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out in the three geopolitical zone of Kaduna State, comprising Makarfi (Kaduna North) Kagarko (Kaduna South) and Igabi (Kaduna Central). A total of 353 serum samples collected, were tested VZV Immunoglobulin G (IgG) antibodies using a commercial IgG enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). The overall seroprevalence rate was 66.3%. Seroprevalence was 51.4% in the age group of 4-6 years, 64.7% in 7-9 years, 68.4 % in 10-12 years and 70.0 % in 13-15 years. The seroprevalence rate of VZV increased with age. There was significant relation between the presence of VZV antibodies and age ($P = 0.000$). There was no significance difference between the presence of VZV antibodies and sex ($P = 0.48$). This data show that the younger age group could be considered as a target group for prevention programs against VZV infection.

KEYWORDS: Seroprevalence; Varicella Zoster Virus, Antibody.

INTRODUCTION

Varicella Zoster Virus (VZV) is a human alphaherpesvirus that causes varicella (chickenpox) as the primary infection and establishes latency in sensory ganglia. VZV reactivation results in herpes zoster (shingles). During the course of varicella and zoster, VZV infects differentiated human cells that exist within unique tissue microenvironments in humans. The tropism of VZV for skin is the most obvious clinical manifestation of VZV infection, producing the vesicular cutaneous lesions that are associated with varicella and zoster (Arvin, 2001a). The clinical pattern of primary VZV infection is highly predictable, beginning with an incubation period of 10–21 days following a close exposure of a susceptible individual to another person with varicella or in some cases, herpes zoster (Arvin, 2001b). Varicella often begins with a prodrome of fever, malaise, headache and abdominal pain. These initial symptoms last about 24–48 h before skin vesicles are noted and are more common in older children and adults (Asano *et al.*, 1990; Koropchak *et al.*, 1991).

Worldwide, varicella is an endemic disease that exhibits a marked seasonal pattern in temperate climates and most temperate climates where this has been studied (Bramley and Jones 2000; Seward *et al.*, 2002; Tobias *et al.*, 1998). The exception is Singapore where seasonality has not been described from surveillance data (Ooi *et al.*, 1992). In temperate and tropical climates, the peak disease incidence is most commonly reported in the cooler, drier months during winter or spring. Periodicity with inter epidemic cycles of 2–5 years is described from many countries (Seward *et al.*, 2000; Tobias *et al.*, 1998)). In temperate climates, greater than 90% of adolescents or young adults are VZV seropositive while in tropical climates, serological studies show higher susceptibility among adults reflecting a higher mean age of infection. Seroprevalence among adolescents or young adults has varied widely from less than 20% in St. Lucia (an island community in the West Indies) to greater than 90% in tropical areas in Brazil and urban Calcutta, India (Lee, 1998; Ooi *et al.*, 1992; Reis *et al.*, 2003). Because of its high incidence in young children, varicella is one of the most common communicable diseases in child care centers and attendance in child care or preschools provides the opportunity for exposure to the varicella zoster virus (VZV) at younger ages. The objective of this study was to provide seroprevalence studies of the varicella zoster virus in among children in Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study was carried out in Kaduna State, comprising of 23 Local Government areas. Three (3) Local governments were randomly selected for the study from each senatorial district and these include Makarfi (Kaduna North) with 11 districts, Kagarko (Kaduna South) with 11 districts and Igabi (Kaduna Central) with 10 districts.

Study Design

This study is a cross-sectional study to determine the prevalence of serum IgG against VZV infection among 353 primary school children between ages of 4-15 years in Kaduna State, Nigeria. Information on the children was obtained through questionnaires. By using the sampling frame of primary schools in the various districts of each local government, one school was randomly picked to represent each district in the local government areas. Questionnaires were given to each pupil picked; a written letter seeking the consent of the subject's parent was also forwarded. Those that consented to the request returned the forms with their demographic data filled in.

Sample collection and analysis

Using a sterile disposable syringe, five milliliters (5ml) of venous blood was drawn from children. The blood samples were centrifuged at 1500 rpm for two minutes; sera were separated and stored at -20°C until tested. The sera were tested for the presence of VZV IgG antibodies using a commercial IgG enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) Kit manufactured by DIAGNOSTIC AUTOMATION, INC. USA. This ELISA uses cell-culture-derived VZV antigens for the detection of anti-VZV IgG antibodies in serum. The absorbance was read at 450 nm using an ELISA micro titer plate reader (Sigma Diagnostic). The presence or absence of anti-VZV-specific IgG antibodies in the test samples was calculated according to the manufacturer's instructions. Results were obtained by comparing the antibody titers with the cut off values of the positive and negative controls.

Statistical Analysis

The data were analyzed using SPSS statistical package version 13 for windows. The chi-square test of association was used to determine differences in the seroprevalence rates in male and female pupils, and to determine the rise in VZV IgG seroprevalence with age.

RESULTS

A total of 353 serum samples collected, were tested VZV IgG antibodies. The overall seroprevalence rate was 66.3%. Seroprevalence was 51.4% in the age group of 4-6 years, 64.7% in 7-9 years, 68.4 % in 10-12 years and 70.0 % in 13-15 years.

Table 1: Distribution of VZV IgG antibody in relation to age

Age group (yrs)	No of samples	No Positive	% Positive
4 – 6	37	19	51.4
7 – 9	85	55	64.7
10 – 12	114	78	68.4
13 – 15	117	82	70

$X^2 = 9.02$, ($P = 0.000$)

Chi-square analysis indicated association ($P=0.000$) between the ages and VZV IgG antibody prevalence.

Table 2: Distribution of VZV IgG antibody in relation to sex

Sex	No of Samples tested	No Positive	% Positive
Male	184	126	68.4
Female	169	108	63.9
Total	353	234	66.3

$X^2 = 0.48$, ($P > 0.05$)

Chi-square analysis indicated no association ($P > 0.05$) between the sexes and VZV IgG antibody prevalence.

The seroprevalence rate of VZV increased with age (Table 1). There was significant relation between the presence of VZV antibodies and age ($P = 0.000$). There was no significance difference between the presence of VZV antibodies and sex ($P = 0.48$), (Table 2).

DISCUSSION

Our results revealed that prevalence of antibodies to varicella increase significantly throughout childhood. The seroprevalence of varicella zoster has been known to increase with age. The older children often go to schools or find themselves in communities often crowded, which brings them in contact with the virus and subsequent development of antibodies. Varicella is generally community acquired, and the rate of contacting it is increased by factors that support crowding and close contact interaction such as public schools. The percentage of cases among young adults may be a cause for alarm since the clinical course of varicella is generally more serious in adults and the incidence of complications is higher. The rise in seroprevalence to over 65% with age has been widely reported in several tropical countries such as the United Arab Emirate, (Uduman *et al*, 2001) and India, (Lokeshwar *et al*, 2000) , while 41% was reported by some investigators in Singapore,(Ooi *et al*, 1992). Possession of protective antibodies to varicella zoster confers immunity in adult life. However, it is also an indication of the endemic nature of this viral infection as there is no routine vaccine policy for it in Nigeria. Immunity is often developed in the individuals after the first episode of the infection and subsequent exposure to the viral agent. Some reports exist of individuals within the adolescence age that lack protective IgG to varicella zoster (Migasena *et al*, 1997).

The studies in many temperate countries reported near universal seropositivity by early adolescence. Swiss and American studies have reported that over 90% of individuals in Europe and the United States acquire immunity before adolescence (Muench, *et al* 1986; Wharton, 1996). (Fairley and Miller, 1996) there was 80% seropositivity by the age of 7 years in Spanish children (Eguliz *et al*, 1987) and 83% seroconversion by the age of 9 years in Japanese children (Taylor-Wiedeman *et al*, 1989).

In our studies, there was no association between seroprevalence with sex showing that sex differences do not play any significant role in the acquisition of the infection.

The virus thrive best in temperate climate and this reflected in the near 100% seroprevalence recorded in these countries. The low seroprevalence in tropical region could therefore be attributed to the fact that high ambient temperature and humidity in the tropics decreases VZV transmission by inactivating the virus in the cutaneous lesions. It is also possible that because of high prevalence of certain other childhood viruses in tropical countries, there is interference with the transmission of varicella zoster and the age of varicella infection is postponed. This view was also expressed by Wilkins *et al*, (1998). The tropical countries should therefore consider the possibility of childhood vaccination with varicella zoster to confer immunity and possible improve of the seroprevalence to the virus. Since the majority of VZV infections occur during the early childhood, the best option to reduce the circulation of wild type VZV in the population would be the immunization of young children. These data are also fundamental for evaluating the suitability of establishing mass varicella vaccination programs. Mass vaccination against VZV should be introduced only if very high coverage can be assured. The impact that a mass vaccination program among children 12-18 months of age could have on the epidemiological trend of the infection must be carefully considered.

CONCLUSION

The finding of this study showed that VZV seroprevalence increased with age in the population studied to a level of 70% in adolescence age. Significant proportions of adolescence are still susceptible to varicella infection. There was no association between seroprevalence of VZV with sex of the subjects studied.

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PREVALENCE OF *Salmonella spp* IN SOME ENVIRONMENTAL SAMPLES FROM SOME HOUSEHOLDS ENGAGED IN LIVESTOCK FARMING IN SOME PARTS OF ZARIA, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Salmonella outbreaks from contaminated water and non animal foods (e.g. produce) are increasingly reported. To address the environment as a potential source of pathogenic *Salmonella*, the prevalence of *Salmonella* in households engaged in livestock farming in Zaria, Kaduna State (Nigeria) was investigated. A total of 336 environmental samples comprising water, soil, manure and vegetable samples were collected from thirty households with livestock while three households without livestock were used as control. Sampling was done from March to September 2006 covering both wet and dry seasons. Seven *Salmonella spp* were obtained: 1(0.65%) during the dry season and 6(3.28%) during the wet season. *Salmonella spp* were detected from manure, water and vegetable samples. A prevalence rate of 2.08% was obtained for *Salmonella spp* in the study location. The rate of detection was higher in the wet season than in the dry season. The detection of this pathogen from the environment represents a potential health risk factor since man is always in continuous interaction with the environment.

Keywords; Prevalence, *Salmonella*, Environment, livestock.

INTRODUCTION

The potential contamination due to animal husbandry operations and the indiscriminate disposal of animal wastes and effluents from livestock applied as fertilizer for crop or silage production constitute an environmental and public health risk (Yang *et al.*, 2004).

Adding manure to the soil has agronomic benefits through the addition of plant nutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium) and organic matter (Gagliardi and Karns, 2002). . Despite the benefits from the use of organic manure, there is a potential health risk from manure into the food chain as a means of pathogen transfer. Nicholson *et al.*, (2000) in the review of issue of pathogens transfer into the food chain from manure applications to land, states that there is a lack of data on 'typical' levels of pathogen in animal manures.

The actual number of pathogens shed is important and this has been found to be affected by a number of factors such as animal age, diet, stress and season (Nicholson *et al.*, 2000). The probability of pathogens being available for transport at the soil surface is also likely to be influenced significantly by the duration and conditions of storage prior to land spreading.

Contaminated manure can contaminate the produce directly through its use as a soil fertilizer or indirectly through infiltration of irrigation water or water used to wash the produce (Doyle, 2000). Sources of microbial pathogens on fresh produce at the preharvest stage include faeces, irrigation water, inadequately composted manure, soil, air, animals and human handling (Buck *et al.*, 2003). Salmonellosis is a disease caused by members of the genus *Salmonella* (Nietfeld and Kennedy, 1999). It is an important cause of diarrheal illness in humans, causing approximately 1.4 million illness and 600 deaths annually in the United States (Brenner *et al.*, 2000). Much of what is known about the epidemiology of salmonellosis comes from outbreak investigations. These investigations have determined that most human infections result from the ingestion of foods of animal origin that are contaminated with *Salmonella* species (Mead *et al.*, 1999) being *Salmonella* of animal origin causes an intestinal infection, characterized by sudden onset of fever, myalgia, cephalagia, abdominal cramps, nausea and vomiting. There is increased risk of exposure among those who work in abattoirs, poultry processing plants and those in contact with animal and their products.

This work examines the role of livestock and its effluents as point source of *Salmonella*.

STUDY AREA

The study area covered were some households engaged in livestock farming in Samaru and Sabo in Sabon Gari L.G.A and Zaria city in Zaria L.G.A of Kaduna State. Sabon Gari local government area is a large urban set up with a population of 246,544 people (FGN Gazzet,2009).The local government is situated along longitude 8° and 9° and latitude 10° and 11° on the world map and is bounded on the east by Soba L.G.A and on the west by Giwa L.G.A on the north by Makarfi L.G.A and south by Zaria L.G.A.While, Zaria local government area has a population of about 277, 187 inhabitants (Population Census, 1991). It is situated on longitude 8° and latitude 9° and it is bounded on the east by Soba L.G.A, west by Giwa L.G.A, north by Sabon Gari L.G.A and on the South by Igabi L.G.A.

Livestock keeping is a common activity in most households in the area ranging from poultry, cow, goat, sheep and ram. The semi intensive and intensive livestock management systems are common while the extensive is rare. Most households had wells situated in their residential area from where water for domestic activities, drinking and water for the animals is obtained. Some households have tap, though tap water is not a constant source of water, wells are the most regularly used. However, some households obtain water from stream or river. A total of three hundred and thirty six samples were analyzed. Three cluster settlements of close proximity to the University of Study (Samaru, Sabon Gari and Zaria city) were randomly selected. Within the cluster, households with livestock were identified and ten households randomly selected from each cluster population.

SAMPLE COLLECTION

Water

Water samples were collected according to the procedure recommended by American Public Health Association (APHA, 1992). Water samples were collected from the available water sources in each household visited comprising of water for domestic activities, drinking and watering of animals. All samples were collected in sterile wide-mouthed, screw-capped 250ml glass bottle, packed in ice during transportation to the laboratory (Postgraduate Laboratory, Department of Microbiology, ABU, Zaria). Samples were analyzed within six hours of collection. From the thirty-three households visited a total of seventy six water samples were collected (thirteen water samples from Samaru, ten from Sabo and nine from Zaria city during the dry season; March-May, giving a total of thirty-two samples). A total of thirty eight water samples were collected during the rainy season; June- August (Ten from Sabo, twelve from Samaru, sixteen from Zaria city) and six water samples from households without livestock in both seasons.

Soil/Manure Samples

During the study period, a total of one hundred and seventy manure samples were collected from the households visited; eighty five were collected during the dry season and eighty five during the wet season. During the dry season, manure was collected from twenty storage sites while sixty five fresh manure samples were collected. In the wet season however, manure was collected from thirty storage sites while fifty five were fresh manure samples. A total of sixty six soil samples were collected during the study period (Ten from each of the three locations and three from control sites in both seasons). All samples were collected aseptically using ethanol-sterilized spatula. A 100g of sample was collected at the designated site at five different points, one from the centre and four different points, on the periphery and mixed together to obtain a representative sample. Samples were transported to the laboratory in sterile plastic bags and analysed within six hours of collection.

Vegetable Samples.

Vegetables available in the study sites during the study period and which were grown on soils where manure was applied as fertilizer were collected. Using 90% ethanol-sterilized scissors; vegetables were cut into sterile containers and taken to the laboratory. A total of twenty four vegetable samples were collected consisting fourteen from Samaru, six from Sabo and four from Zaria city. Analysis was done within six hours of collection.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Salmonella was isolated from the samples using Selenite F broth enrichment and incubation (Harvey and Price 1979). Ten millilitres of each water sample was combined with equal volume of sterile double strength Selenite F broth and incubated at 37°C for 24h followed by streaking for isolation on *Salmonella-Shigella* agar. Isolation from soil and manure samples was by pre-enrichment of one gram of sample in nine millilitres of peptone water followed by enrichment in Selenite F broth and incubation at 37°C for 24h. The washed and cut vegetable was pre-enriched in Selenite F broth and incubated at 37°C for 24h. After the enrichment methods, *Salmonella* was detected by plating on *Salmonella-Shigella* (SS) agar for 24h at 37°C. Mixed cultures were transferred to fresh SS agar plates and streaked out to obtain pure colonies. Typical *Salmonella* colonies which appear colourless with black centers were picked and independently confirmed by Gram staining. Isolates were stored on slants of nutrient agar after incubation at 37°C for 24h. The slants were presumptive *Salmonella* isolates.

All the presumptive isolates were subjected to series of biochemical tests (indole, methyl red, citrate, Voges Proskauer, triple sugar iron, motility and oxidase test.). Biochemical identification of isolates was as described by Singleton (1997) and Farmer (1999).

Isolates suspected to be *Salmonella* were serologically tested using *Salmonella* polyvalent 'O' group A-Z antiserum latex kit according to the instructions of the manufacturer (Oxoid) Basingstoke, Hampshire, England). All isolates were streaked on blood agar plates and incubated at 37°C for 24h. Latex reagents were brought to room temperature, one drop of the test latex was dispensed onto a circle on the reaction card and a drop of saline was placed on the circle distant from the latex. Using a loop, a portion of the colony of presumptive *Salmonella spp* on blood agar plates was emulsified in the saline drop on a portion of the circle on the card. The test latex and the resulting smooth suspension were mixed together and spread to cover the reaction area using the loop. The card was rocked in a circular motion observing for agglutination within one minute. Agglutination of the test latex within one minute was recorded as positive result.

The association between the detection of pathogens and location was assessed using chi-square test of association and analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used for pair wise multiple comparison of mean counts from the three locations.

RESULTS

Analysis of questionnaire showed that the intensive (confined) and semi intensive (allowed to move around) livestock management systems were predominant in the study area. Of the thirty households with livestock visited, 16 (53.3%) practiced the intensive management system 5 (31.3%) in Sabo, 6 (37.5%) in Samaru and 5 (31.3%) in Zaria city. The remaining households 14 (6.7%) practiced semi intensive management system; 6 (42.9%) in Sabo, 4 (28.6 %) in Samaru and 4 (28.6%) in Zaria city. Among the households visited, 10 (33.3%) own poultry, 8 (26.7%) own cows, 10 (33.3%) own goats and 2 (6.7%) own sheep. On the method of manure disposal, 19 (63.3%) dispose manure in the bush around the house, 5 (16.7%) dispose manure on the farm, 5 (16.7%) dispose manure near the farm and 1 (3.3%) dispose theirs just beside the house in heaps. In response to domestic water source, 22 (73.3%) obtain water from wells, 6 (20%) from tap and 2 (6.7%) obtain water from river/stream. Among the households visited, only 8 (26.7%) had vegetable farm and use manure to fertilize them.

A total of 336 environmental samples (water, soil, manure and vegetables) were analyzed to detect the presence of *Salmonella spp*. Table 1 shows that 104 (30.95%) samples were collected from Sabo, 107 (31.85%) from Zaria city and 125 (37.20%) from Samaru.

Sixty five isolates of *Salmonella spp* were obtained. Twenty three (35.38%) were presumptive for *Salmonella spp*. and 7(30.43%) were confirmed *Salmonella spp* against *Salmonella* antiserum. Two out of 104 samples from Sabo, four out of 125 samples from Samaru and one out of 107 samples from Zaria city were positive for *Salmonella spp* (Table 1).

TABLE 1 Samples containing pathogens in the locations studied

Location	Source of samples	Total no of samples	<i>Salmonella</i> isolates
Sabo	Water	26	-
	Soil	22	-
	Manure	50	2
	Vegetables	6	-
Sub total		104	2
Samaru	Water	25	2
	Soil	22	-
	Manure	64	2
	Vegetables	14	-
Subtotal		125	4
Zaria city	Water	25	-
	Soil	22	-
	Manure	56	-
	Vegetables	4	1
Subtotal		107	1
Overall total		336	7(2.08)

Key = Pathogen not detected from samples. Isolation Frequency = $\frac{\text{No. of samples containing pathogens}}{\text{No of samples analysed}}$

TABLE 2 Prevalence of pathogens in environmental samples by season

Pathogens by Season	Location			Total	Isolation frequency of pathogens (%)
	Sabo	Samaru	Zaria city		
<i>Salmonella spp</i>					
D153	-	1	-	1	1(0.65)
W183	2	3	1	6	6(3.28)

Key
 - = pathogen not detected from samples.
 D=Dry season
 W=Wet season
 N=Number of samples collected

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STUDIES ON ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF *Adenium obesum* (*Apocynaceae*) STEM-BARK

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ABSTRACT

Antibacterial evaluation of the methanolic and petroleum spirit (60-80) °C extracts of the stem-bark of *adenium obesum* was carried out using agar- well diffusion method. The extracts were tested against some selected standard gram negative bacteria strains–*Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC- 25619), *Salmonella typhi*(ATCC 9184), *Neisseria gonorrhoea* (NCTC 8198), *Klebsiella pneumonia*(ATCC 15380). Antimicrobial sensitivity test of the extracts at concentration of $4 \times 10^4 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ showed significant zones of inhibition against 80% of the tested organisms. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of the extracts against the listed organisms ranges from $1 \times 10^4 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ to $4 \times 10^4 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ and $3 \times 10^4 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ to $5 \times 10^4 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ for Crude extracts of the methanol and petroleum spirit respectively. Phytochemical examination of the extracts revealed the presence of alkaloids, steroids, saponins, glycosides, anthraquinones, tannins and flavonoids. These findings reveal broad spectrum activity of the plant stem-bark extracts.

KEYWORDS: Gram Negative, bacterial studies, Stem-bark, *Adenium obesum*

INTRODUCTION:

The African environment is probably the least explored in terms of available untapped resources. Herbal medicine is readily available in our diverse vegetation, cheap and above all carries the potentials of introducing new templates into modern medicine.

The use of medicinal plants all over the world predates the introduction of antibiotics and other modern drugs into African continent (Akinyemi *et al*, 2005). Herbal medicine has been widely used and formed an integral part of primary health care in China (Liu, 1987) Ethiopia (Desta, 1993) Argentina (Anesini and Perez, 1993) and Papua New Guinea (Nick *et al*, 1995). A significant proportion of pharmaceutical products in current use are designed from plants (Cowan, 1999 and Rankin *et al*, 2002). A large number of phytochemicals belonging to several chemical classes have been shown to have inhibitory effect on all types of micro-organisms in vitro (Cowan, 1999) and some plant extracts have shown activity on both gram negative and gram positive organism (Nascimento *et al*, 2000) .

The use of various plant parts in the treatment of the sick developed into tradition which was handed down from one generation to another over the years verbally or written (Sofowora, 1982; Akinyanju, 1986). For thousands of years, medicine depended exclusively on leaves, flowers and barks of plants, only recently have synthetic drugs come into use and in many instances, these are replicas of chemicals identified in plants (Conway, 1973). In orthodox medicine, a plant may be subjected to several chemical processes before its active ingredients is extracted refined and made ready for consumption, while in traditional medicine, a plant is simply eaten raw, cooked or infused in water or native wine or even prepared as food (Conway, 1973).

Even before the discovery of modern antibiotics and other chemotherapeutic agents, traditional medicine has served as man's resort when attacked by infective agents such as bacteria and fungi (Crafton, 1983).

The effects of plant extracts on bacteria have been studied by a very large number of researchers in different parts of the world. Much work has been done on enthno-medicinal plants in Nigeria and Africa. Nevertheless, the increased incidence of diseases for which there is yet an effective remedy is a driving factor for more screening programmes. Diseases like tuberculosis, pneumonia, typhoid fever, rheumatic fever and meningitis

(Greenwood *et al.*, 1992) still pose a major challenge to modern chemotherapeutic agents. It is in this context that the stem-bark of *adenium obesum* was screened for antibacterial activity.

Adenium obesum belongs to the family *Apocyanaceae*. It is a Succulent shrub or small tree, up to 4(–6) m tall, sometimes with a fleshy taproot; stem swollen at base up to 1(–2) m in diameter; bark pale greyish-green, grey or brown, smooth, with sticky, clear or white latex; branchlets glabrescent, pubescent at apex. Leaves arranged spirally, clustered at the end of branchlets, simple; stipules minute or absent; petiole up to 4 mm long; blade linear to obovate, 3–12(–17) cm × 0.2–6 cm, base cuneate, apex acute to rounded or emarginate, entire, slightly glaucous, dull green or pale green, leathery, pinnately veined with distinct or indistinct lateral veins (Rowley,1983).

The plant is important in traditional medicine. In the Sahel a decoction from the roots, alone or in combination with other plants, is used to treat venereal diseases; a root or bark extract is used as a bath or lotion to treat skin diseases and to kill lice, while latex is applied to decaying teeth and septic wounds. In Somalia a root decoction as nose drops is prescribed for rhinitis. In northern Kenya latex is rubbed on the head against lice and powdered stems are applied to kill skin parasites of camels and cattle. The bark is chewed as an abortifacient (Neuwinger, 2000).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and Preparation of Plant Material

The stem-bark of *Adenium obesum* was collected from Samara–Zaria, Kaduna State of Nigeria. It was confirmed and authenticated at the Herbarium of the Department of Biological Sciences, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria where a voucher specimen was deposited. The bark was air dried and ground into powdered form using a porcelain mortar and pestle. It was then preserved well in polythene bag and stored in a dessicator before subsequent experiments.

Extraction

The powdered stem-bark of *Adenium obesum* (500g) were packed into a thimble and placed inside a soxhlet extractor and extracted exhaustively and respectively with petroleum spirit (60-80) °C and methanol. The extracts were concentrated *in vacuo* at 40 °C using rotary evaporator, after which the crude extracts were obtained from the solvents.

Phytochemical screening

The petroleum and methanolic extracts of the stem-bark of *Adenium obesum* were subjected to

Preliminary phytochemical tests using standard techniques (Trease and Evans, 1989; Sofowora, 1993).

Test microorganisms

Five standard Gram-negative bacterial strains were selected; *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC- 25619), *Salmonella typhi* (ATCC 9184), *Neisseria gonorrhoea* (NCTC 8198) and *Klebsiella pneumonia* (ATCC 15380).The bacterial strains were maintained on nutrient agar and sub-cultured every three days. An inoculum of each bacterial strain was suspended in 5 ml of Mueller Hinton broth (MHB) and incubated overnight at 37 °C. The overnight cultures were diluted with Mueller Hinton broth and adjusted to give a concentration of bacterial cells equivalent to a McFarland 0.5 standard prior to the bacterial testing (Samie *et al.*, 2005).

Susceptibility testing

The agar cup diffusion method was used for this test. Sterile nutrient agar plates were flooded with appropriately diluted microorganism, the excess was aseptically drained and the surface, allowed to dry at room temperature. Wells were bored into the agar plates using a 4 mm sterile cork borer and 0.1 ml each of the extracts at concentration of $4 \times 10^4 \mu\text{g} / \text{cm}^3$ was introduced into each well. The plates were allowed a pre-diffusion time of 1 h at room temperature and then incubated at 37°C for 24 h after which zones of inhibition were read to the nearest millimeter.

Minimum inhibitory concentration [MIC]

A series of culture tubes (microdilution assays) were prepared all containing the same volume of medium inoculated with test microorganisms (Ferreira *et al*, 2003). The lowest concentration of sample at which the subculture from test dilution yielded no viable organisms was recorded as minimum inhibitory concentration (Nazaruk and Jakoniuk, 2005). Decreasing concentration of petroleum spirit or methanol extracts of *Adenium obesum* (AO) extracts was added to the tubes usually a step wise dilution (two fold serial dilutions) was used starting from highest to lowest concentrations. One tube was left without AO extracts to serve as positive control and other without extract and inoculums to serve as negative control. The cultures were incubated at a temperature optimal for growth of the test organism and a period of time sufficient for growth for at least 10-15 generations (usually 24 hours for bacteria at 37 ° C). The tubes were inspected visually to determine the growth of microorganisms by the presence of turbidity and the tubes in which AO extract is present in minimum concentration sufficient to inhibit the microbial growth which remains clear was noted as MIC of the extract. In experimental terms MIC is the concentration of the AO extracts present in the last clear tube that is the tube having the lowest antibiotic concentration in which growth is not observed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Phytochemical constituents of the stem-bark of *Adenium obesum*

Constituents	Extract	
	Petroleum spirit	Methanol
Alkaloids	–	+
Flavonoids	–	+
Saponins	+	+
Glycosides	+	+
Anthrquinones	–	+
Tannins	+	+
Steroids	+	+
Coumarins	–	–

+/_ = presence or absence of constituent tested

Table 2: Antibacterial sensitivity tests of the crude extracts of *Adenium obesum* (stem-bark) at Concentration of $4 \times 10^4 \mu\text{g} / \text{cm}^3$: Zone of Inhibition (mm).

Test organisms	Zone of Inhibition (mm)	
	Methanolic extract	Petroleum spirit extract.
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (ATCC 25922)	26	20
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (ATCC- 25619)	-	-
<i>Salmonella typhi</i> (ATCC 9184)	20	16
<i>Neisseria gonorrhoea</i> (NCTC 8198)	27	17
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i> (ATCC 15380)	22	22

- = No zone of inhibition

Table 3. Minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) of the petroleum spirit and ethanol extracts of the stem-bark *Adenium obesum*

Microorganism	MIC ($\times 10^4 \mu\text{g} / \text{cm}^3$)	
	Petroleum spirit extract	Methanol extract
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (ATCC 25922)	4	2
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (ATCC- 25619)	NG	NG
<i>Salmonella typhi</i> (ATCC 9184)	5	3
<i>Neisseria gonorrhoea</i> (NCTC 8198)	4	2
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i> (ATCC 15380)	3	3

NG = No Growth

Preliminary phytochemical screening: The preliminary phytochemical screening of the plant extracts revealed the presence of alkaloids, steroids, saponins, glycosides, anthraquinones, tannins and flavonoids in the methanol extract. However, coumarins were absent in the extract. While the petroleum spirit extract contained only saponins, glycosides, tannins and steroids; alkaloids, flavonoids, anthraquinones and coumarins were absent (Table 1). The methanolic crude extract contained more secondary metabolites than the petroleum spirit extract probably because of the polarity of the solvent (methanol). Methanol as more polar solvent is capable of extracting both the polar and the non-polar components of the plant stem-bark and hence having more metabolites in it.

Antimicrobial tests: The plant extracts have demonstrated significant antimicrobial activity against the microorganisms. The two extracts (methanol and petroleum spirit) are active against four out of the five organisms tested. The inhibition zones for methanolic extract, which ranges from 20-27mm, were generally higher than that of petroleum spirit; with range from 16-22mm (Table 2). This reveals greater antimicrobial activity of the methanolic extract compared with that of petroleum spirit.

MIC values of the methanolic extract were smaller (more active) than that of petroleum spirit. The smallest MIC ($2 \times 10^4 \mu\text{g} / \text{cm}^3$) was obtained with *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922) and *Neisseria gonorrhoea* (NCTC 8198). This is a good manifestation of antibacterial activity of AO extract. For the petroleum spirit extract the MIC values for the same microorganisms was $4 \times 10^4 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$. The highest MIC value for the AO methanolic extract was $3 \times 10^4 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ against *Salmonella typhi* (ATCC 9184) and *Klebsiella pneumonia* (ATCC 15380), while that of petroleum spirit extract is $5 \times 10^4 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ against *Salmonella typhi* (ATCC 9184). The two extracts did not have any inhibitory effect on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC- 25619), Table 3.

The results of this study reveal the antibacterial activity of stem-bark of AO on the selected gram-negative bacteria. The methanolic extract seems to be more active against the microorganisms than the petroleum spirit extract and this could be ascribed to its ability to extract more active principles. Although the methanolic extract exhibited higher activity, but generally, the plant manifested significant therapeutic potentials. This is not surprising because the plant contains highly active compounds with antibacterial activities. There are tannins which are reported to have various physiological effects like anti-irritant, antisecretolytic, antiphlogistic, antimicrobial and antiparasitic effects. Phytotherapeutically tannin-containing plants are used to treat nonspecific diarrhoea, inflammations of mouth and throat and slightly injured skins (Westendarp, 2006; Trease and Evans, 2000). Steroids are also there, which are important drugs used as hypotensives, cardiac depressants, sedatives and anti-dysenteric agents (Abdul, 1990). The glycosides which are used as laxative and cathartic drugs

were confirmed. Alkaloids that act as anti-malarial, anti-amoebic agents, astringents were present (Abdul, 1990).

Results obtained from this study could form a good basis for selection of AO for further phytochemical and pharmacological investigations. The antibacterial properties of AO can be exploited for potential development of new drugs against infectious diseases caused by the selected pathogens.

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STIMULATORY EFFECTS OF CALCIUM CARBONATE ON BUTANOL PRODUCTION BY SOLVENTOGENIC *Clostridium* species

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ABSTRACT

Solventogenic *Clostridium* species are motile Gram positive anaerobic bacteria used for the fermentative production of acetone-butanol-ethanol (ABE). The addition of CaCO₃ to semi-defined P2 medium was investigated to evaluate its impact on growth, amelioration of butanol toxicity, glucose utilization, and ABE production by solventogenic *Clostridium* species. Two *Clostridium* species commonly used in industrial production of fermentative-derived ABE were used in the study. Under culture conditions of the present study, CaCO₃ enhanced growth of and total ABE production by solventogenic *Clostridium* species (*C. acetobutylicum* ATCC 824 and *C. beijerinckii* 260 produced more than 24 and 22 g/L ABE, respectively) by 31% to 46%. Dramatically increased growth of solventogenic *Clostridium* species and fermentation rate resulted in greater ABE concentration and productivity for treatments containing CaCO₃ relative to the control with no CaCO₃ addition. The addition of CaCO₃ into P2 medium, in addition, increased butanol tolerance by more than 40% indicating that elevated levels of ABE produced by solventogenic *Clostridium* species may have occurred due to enhanced tolerance of butanol in the presence of CaCO₃.

KEYWORDS: Butanol, acetone, *Clostridium beijerinckii*, *Clostridium acetobutylicum*, Calcium carbonate, biofuel

INTRODUCTION

Interest in biofuel production has grown recently due to continuous depletion of worldwide oil deposits, awareness in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions during combustion of fossil fuels, and potential impacts of this activity on global warming. Ethanol is currently the most important renewable liquid biofuel, but it has problems ranging from lesser energy content than gasoline, blending limitations with gasoline, potential for corrosion of pipes, and inability to be transported using existing pipeline infrastructure (Ezeji and Blaschek, 2010). The acetone butanol ethanol (ABE) fermentation process is of particular interest for the production of fuels and chemicals from renewable resources because butanol has superior attributes over other fermentation-derived fuels, including ethanol (Ezeji and Blaschek, 2007). Butanol, currently manufactured with petroleum feedstock, has a lower vapor pressure than ethanol which makes it less flammable, safer to transport, and safer to use in combustion engines than ethanol (Dürre, 2008). Major challenges with ABE fermentation are limitations such as low ABE concentration, yield, and productivity due to butanol toxicity to microbial cells (Ezeji *et al.*, 2003; 2004). Currently, butanol is not used as a biofuel because of cost. However, David Ramsey, Environmental Energy Inc., The Ohio State University, drove an unmodified 1992 Buick 10,000 miles across the USA using only butanol as a fuel (Ezeji and Blaschek, 2007).

With the history of bio-butanol production by the natural solvent-producing *Clostridium* species such as *Clostridium acetobutylicum* 824, and *Clostridium beijerinckii* 260, there are some clear inherent advantages in improving and using these native clostridial systems for producing bio-butanol (Ezeji *et al.*, 2010). The ABE concentration and productivity in a typical batch fermentation by solventogenic *Clostridium* species can be increased to values between 13 to 18 g/L and 0.2 to 0.3 g/L/h, respectively (Ezeji and Blaschek, 2008). Modest increases in ABE titer and productivity can be achieved by incorporating acetate into fermentation medium (Chen and Blaschek, 1999; Gu *et al.*, 2009). Studies focused on butanol removal from the fermentation broth using distillation showed that, as the concentration of butanol increased from 10 g/L to 40 g/L, ratio of oil to

fuel used for 100% recovery of butanol decreased from 1.5 t/t to 0.25 t/t (Philips and Humphrey, 1983). This suggests that significant energy savings can be achieved if the concentration of butanol in the fermentation beer is increased.

ABE production is by biphasic fermentation process in which acetic and butyric acid are produced inside the microbial cells with concomitant release into the environment during the acidogenic phase followed by re-assimilation of the acid into the cells and conversion into ABE (solventogenic phase) (Ezeji *et al.*, 2010). It is noteworthy that excessive accumulation of undissociated acetic and butyric acid in the bioreactor during ABE fermentation is detrimental to nutrient uptake by and growth of solventogenic *Clostridium* species (Herrero *et al.*, 1985).

The objective of this study was to examine the effect of CaCO₃ addition in chemically semi-defined media on growth and ABE production by solventogenic *Clostridium* species. Although the two microorganisms used for the study have significant differences in both genome and physiology (Nolling *et al.*, 2001), we investigated whether the effect of CaCO₃ is species and strain specific or non-selective in action.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Microorganism, culture maintenance and inoculums development

Microorganisms used for this study were *Clostridium acetobutylicum* ATCC 824 and *Clostridium beijerinckii* 260. *C. acetobutylicum* ATCC 824 was obtained from America Type Culture Collection in Manassas, Virginia, USA, while *C. beijerinckii* 260 was obtained from Professor David Jones. Laboratory stocks of *C. beijerinckii* 260 and *C. acetobutylicum* ATCC 824 were routinely maintained as spore suspensions in sterile double distilled water at 4 °C. *C. acetobutylicum* ATCC 824 spores (200 ml) was heat shocked for 10 min at 75 °C, while *C. beijerinckii* 260 was heat shocked for 3 min at 65 °C followed by cooling on ice. The heat shocked spores were inoculated into 10 mL anoxic pre-sterilized tryptone–glucose–yeast extract (TGY) medium (Ezeji *et al.*, 2003, 2004) and incubated anaerobically for 12 to 14 h at 35 ± 1 °C. *C. beijerinckii* 260 spores may take up to 18 h before any visible growth can be seen. This was followed by transferring 8 mL of actively growing culture (12–14 h old) to 92 mL anoxic pre-sterilized tryptone–glucose–yeast extract (TGY) medium. To create anaerobic conditions and prepare anoxic medium, loosely capped bottles with sterilized TGY medium were kept in the anaerobic chamber (Coy Laboratory Products Inc., Ann Arbor, Michigan) with modified atmosphere of 82% N₂, 15% CO₂, and 3% H₂ for 24 h to facilitate exchange of gases between TGY medium and gases in anaerobic chamber. Cells were grown anaerobically at 35 °C for 4 to 5 h during which the optical density of cells at 540 nm λ attained 0.9-1.1 (pre-culture).

Effect of calcium carbonate on *Clostridium* species growth and ABE production

Various concentrations (2-10 g/L) of CaCO₃ were added into 250 mL Pyrex screw capped bottles containing 60 g/L glucose and 1 g/L yeast extract. The mixture was sterilized at 121 °C for 15 min. On cooling to 37 °C, the bottles were transferred into an anaerobic chamber at 35 °C for 24 h for anaerobiosis. This was followed by addition of filter-sterilized P2 stock solutions and inoculation with pre-culture (*C. acetobutylicum* ATCC 824 or *C. beijerinckii* 260) as described previously (Ezeji *et al.*, 2003). Samples (5 mL) were collected every 12 h for cell concentration, ABE, glucose and acid analysis. Unless otherwise stated, all fermentations were conducted in triplicate with the cultures grown with no agitation at 35°C, and no special measures taken to control pH.

Effect of calcium carbonate on protein expression in *Clostridium* species

To evaluate whether addition of CaCO₃ into growth medium enhanced protein expression in *Clostridium* species, *C. beijerinckii* cells were harvested from P2 medium (control) and P2 medium plus CaCO₃ (treatment) fermentation and used for analysis. To eliminate bias in protein concentration due to cell concentration, control and treatment cells were adjusted to same optical density at 540 nm wave length using DU800 spectrophotometer. *C. beijerinckii* cells were lysed with TissueLyser LT (Qiagen Inc., Valencia, CA), centrifuged at 14,000 x g for 10min and supernatant was used as crude protein. Aliquots of the crude protein were loaded onto SDS gel followed by SDS-PAGE analysis following standard procedure.

Analytical procedures

Growth of *C. acetobutylicum* ATCC 824 or *C. beijerinckii* 260 was estimated by measuring OD₅₄₀ using a DU800 spectrophotometer (Beckman Coulter Inc., Brea, CA). ABE and acid (acetic & butyric) concentrations were measured using a 7890A Agilent Technologies gas chromatograph (Agilent Technologies Inc., Wilmington, DE) equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID) and 30 m (length) x 320 µm (internal diameter) x 0.50 µm (HP-Innowax film) J x W 19091N-213 capillary column. ABE productivity, or rate of production, was calculated as total ABE produced (g/L culture volume) divided by fermentation time (h). Glucose concentration was determined using a hexokinase and glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase coupled enzymatic assay (Ezeji and Bahl, 2006). Glucose utilization rate was calculated as total glucose utilized by solventogenic *Clostridium* species (g/L culture volume) divided by fermentation time (h). Yield was defined as total grams of ABE produced per total grams of glucose utilized.

To evaluate whether addition of CaCO₃ into growth medium reduced the toxic effect of butanol on *Clostridium* species, *C. acetobutylicum* 824 and *C. beijerinckii* 260 were grown in P2 medium containing 0-20 g/L butanol and incubated in an anaerobic chamber at 35 °C for 24 h as described above.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of CaCO₃ on growth, pH and acetic-butyric acid production by solventogenic *Clostridium* species

To evaluate impact of CaCO₃ on growth of solventogenic *Clostridium* species, batch fermentations were conducted with P2 medium containing different concentrations of CaCO₃. The growth of *C. acetobutylicum* was enhanced in the presence of different concentrations of CaCO₃ (Fig. 1) reaching average maximum cell density of 9.31 (Table 1A) which resulted in about a 2-fold increase in growth when compared to the control.

Figure 1: Optical density of *C. acetobutylicum* 824 (measure of cell growth) obtained during batch ABE fermentation in P2 medium containing different concentrations (0-10 g/L) of CaCO₃. The data represent the averages of ≥ 3 fermentations.

Similar results were obtained with *C. beijerinckii* 260 (Table 1B) where average optical density reached 8.98. With the exception of the 2 g/L CaCO₃ treatment, no significant difference in glucose utilization among other (4 to 10 g/L) CaCO₃ treatments (data not shown) was observed. Hence optimal concentration of CaCO₃ for the growth of solventogenic *Clostridium* species is 4 g/L. Because CaCO₃ enhanced solventogenic *Clostridium* species cell growth to a great extent, we determined the effect of CaCO₃ on the rate of glucose utilization. We compared results obtained from fermentations containing no CaCO₃ supplementation (control) with fermentations containing 4 g/L CaCO₃ (Table 1A and 1B). Addition of 4 g/L CaCO₃ to fermentation medium resulted in a glucose utilization rate of 1.2 g/Lh compared to the control whose values ranged from 0.6 to 0.8 g/Lh glucose (Table 1A and 1B), a 50 – 100% increase. ABE fermentation under conditions of excess glucose (60 g/L) is typical because excess sugar in the fermentation medium is essential for maintenance of solvent production (Jones and Woods, 1986). At the end of fermentation, however, about 10-20 g/L glucose is left in the bioreactor due to inability of *Clostridium* species to use all substrates in the presence of relatively high

butanol concentrations (Grupe and Gottschalk, 1992; Qureshi and Blaschek, 2000; Ezeji *et al.*, 2007a, 2007b). In the presence of CaCO₃, residual concentration of glucose in the bioreactor was zero following 48 h fermentation by *C. beijerinckii* (Table 1B). Past economic analysis demonstrated that the fermentation substrate was one of the most important factors that influenced the cost of fermentation-derived butanol production (Qureshi and Blaschek, 2000).

Table 1A: Total sugar utilized, ABE produced, ABE yield and productivity obtained during batch ABE fermentation by *C. acetobutylicum* ATCC 824 in the presence 4 g/L CaCO₃. No CaCO₃ was present in the control.

Parameters (Max. values)	Control	CaCO ₃ treatment
Acetone (g/L)	3.66 ± 0.44	7.62 ± 0.26
Ethanol (g/L)	1.30 ± 0.04	1.16 ± 0.20
Butanol (g/L)	11.43 ± 1.00	14.78 ± 0.32
Total ABE (g/L)	16.39 ± 1.45	24.01 ± 0.73
Initial glucose (g/L)	60.17 ± 0.53	59.28 ± 0.83
Final glucose (g/L)	16.02 ± 1.23	1.61 ± 0.63
Cell density (540 nm)	5.47 ± 0.09	9.31 ± 0.21
Fermentation time (h)	72	48
Total glucose utilized (g)	44.15 ± 0.71	57.68 ± 0.20
Glucose utilization rate (g/Lh)	0.61 ± 0.01	1.2 ± 0.0
ABE Yield (g/g)	0.37 ± 0.03	0.42 ± 0.01
ABE Productivity (g/L/h)	0.23 ± 0.02	0.50 ± 0.04

Table 1B: Total sugar utilized, ABE produced, ABE yield and productivity obtained during batch ABE fermentation by *C. beijerinckii* 260 in the presence 4 g/L CaCO₃. No CaCO₃ was present in the control.

Parameters (Max. values)	Control	CaCO ₃ treatment
Acetone (g/L)	5.06 ± 0.14	7.40 ± 0.33
Ethanol (g/L)	0.88 ± 0.04	1.39 ± 0.04
Butanol (g/L)	11.38 ± 0.24	13.89 ± 0.14
Total ABE (g/L)	17.31 ± 0.15	22.68 ± 0.44
Initial glucose (g/L)	59.07 ± 1.8	58.63 ± 0.6
Final glucose (g/L)	10.6 ± 0.34	0
Cell density (540 nm)	4.89 ± 0.34	8.98 ± 0.31
Fermentation time (h)	60	48
Total glucose utilized (g)	48.47 ± 1.02	58.63 ± 0.6
Glucose utilization rate (g/Lh)	0.81 ± 0.02	1.22 ± 0.0
ABE Yield (g/g)	0.36 ± 0.01	0.40 ± 0.004
ABE Productivity (g/L/h)	0.29 ± 0.003	0.47 ± 0.01

Complete utilization of glucose by *C. beijerinckii* 260 (Table 1B) in batch fermentation has the potential to improve the economics of fermentation-derived butanol production and effluent disposal.

Figure 2: The pH profile obtained during batch ABE fermentation by *C. acetobutylicum* 824 in P2 medium containing different concentrations of CaCO_3 . The data represent the averages of ≥ 3 fermentations.

Furthermore, during growth of solventogenic *C. acetobutylicum*, low pH < 5.5 (Fig. 2) and accumulation of acetic-butyric acid (Fig. 3A and 3B) in the bioreactor are necessary for the initiation of ABE production (Ezeji *et al.*, 2010). As a result, the effect of CaCO_3 upon pH and acid production were measured. The elevated concentrations of total acid measured at 0 h fermentation originated from P2 medium component (ammonium acetate) and in all fermentations, solventogenesis was initiated at the fermentation time of 12 h (Fig. 2, Fig. 3A-B). The pH decreased sharply following 12 h fermentation and the subsequent decrease has no linear relationship with total acids produced during the course of fermentation (Fig. 2, Fig. 3A-B).

This observation agrees with previous related reports (Andersch and Gottschalk, 1982; Bahl *et al.*, 1982; Grupe and Gottschalk, 1992) which demonstrated this pattern of pH and total acid fluctuation during growth of solventogenic *Clostridium* species and initiation of solventogenesis. Thorough examination of Figures 2A and 2B shows that greater concentration of acetic-butyric acid was produced by fermentations with CaCO_3 than the control with no CaCO_3 . This greater concentration of acetic-butyric acid, however, did not result in a lower pH than the control due to modulation of dissociated and undissociated acetic-butyric acid by CaCO_3 .

Figure 3: Acetic acid (A) and butyric acid (B) production profiles obtained during batch ABE fermentation by *C. acetobutylicum* 824 in P2 medium containing different concentrations of CaCO₃. The data represent the averages of ≥ 3 fermentations.

Poorly buffered fermentation medium will lead to excessive accumulation of undissociated acetic and butyric acid, which is detrimental to nutrient uptake, cell growth, and ABE production (Ezeji *et al.*, 2010). Bryant and Blaschek (1988) reported previously an increased buffering capacity of the fermentation medium led to enhanced butanol production although maximum butanol concentration achieved in their investigation was 10 g/L compared to 14.78 g/L butanol (Table 1A) and 13.89 (Table 1B), a 39 – 48% increase, in the present study. Modulation of equilibrium between dissociated and undissociated acetic-butyric acid in fermentation medium, in addition, has been thought to be vital for optimal butanol production by solventogenic *Clostridium* species (Ezeji *et al.*, 2010). Excessive buffering will also have a negative impact on butanol production but maintenance of optimal buffering condition in the bioreactor during ABE fermentation for optimal butanol production is crucial.

Effect of CaCO₃ on butanol production, productivity and yield by solventogenic *Clostridium* species

Figure 4: Total butanol (A) and ABE (B) production profiles obtained during batch ABE fermentation by *C. acetobutylicum* 824 in P2 medium containing different concentrations of

Having ascertained that impact of CaCO₃ on solventogenic *Clostridium* species growth was not specific for *C. acetobutylicum*, rather exerts same effect on other solventogenic *Clostridium* species, *C. beijerinckii*, the ABE production characteristics of *C. acetobutylicum* 824 and *C. beijerinckii* 260 grown in P2 medium containing various concentrations (2g/L-10g/L) of CaCO₃ was conducted and results are presented in Figure 4A-B and Table 1A (*C. acetobutylicum* 824) and Table 1B (*C. beijerinckii* 260). Control fermentations of *C. acetobutylicum* and *C. beijerinckii* without CaCO₃ produced maximum butanol concentration of 11.43 g/L and 11.38 g/L, respectively (Tables 1A-B). Increasing CaCO₃ concentration in the fermentation medium resulted in enhanced butanol and total ABE production by *C. acetobutylicum* but increase in butanol and ABE production peaked at 4 g/L CaCO₃ (Fig. 4A-B). Similar results were obtained with *C. beijerinckii* (Figure 5). Hence optimal concentration of CaCO₃ for butanol production is 4 g/L.

Figure 5: Total ABE production profile obtained during batch ABE fermentation by *C. beijerinckii* 260 in P2 medium containing different concentrations of CaCO_3 . The data represent the averages of ≥ 3 fermentations.

When total ABE produced by CaCO_3 treatment was compared to respective controls of solventogenic *Clostridium* species, *C. acetobutylicum* and *C. beijerinckii* achieved a 46% and 31% increase in ABE production, respectively. ABE productivity by *C. acetobutylicum* and *C. beijerinckii* 8052 was increased by 117% and 62%, respectively (Table 1A-B). ABE yield in solventogenic *Clostridium* species was increased as well by CaCO_3 ranging from 11% to 13% (Table 1A-B). Incorporation of CaCO_3 into fermentation medium, in addition, resulted in a 24 h reduction in fermentation time (48 h) and more importantly in efficient utilization of glucose (Tables 1A-B).

CaCO_3 and total protein expression in solventogenic *Clostridium* species

As part of initial efforts to unravel the molecular basis for the dramatic increase in ABE production and glucose utilization by solventogenic *Clostridium* species that is induced by CaCO_3 , we inquired if there was up-regulation of select proteins. By using OD_{540} values, we first normalized the amount of cells in the control and CaCO_3 treatment (~ 1.8 mg dry weight cells) and ensured that any increase in protein levels detected would be directly attributable to increased protein synthesis and not cell growth. The total crude lysates obtained from these cells were then subjected to SDS-PAGE analysis (Ezeji and Blaschek, 2006). Indeed, in *C. beijerinckii* grown in P2 medium with CaCO_3 , there is a noticeable increase in the abundance of several proteins; this increase is both proportional to the amount of CaCO_3 in the medium and the time of fermentation (Fig. 6). While it is conceivable that these up-regulated proteins might be involved in glucose uptake and utilization, such an idea will await confirmation by our future proteomic investigations.

Figure 6: SDS-PAGE of total proteins of *C. beijerinckii* cells harvested at fermentation time of 36 h (line 1-6) and 48 h (line 7-12) during batch ABE fermentation in P2 medium containing different concentrations of CaCO₃. Lines 1-6 are samples from P2 medium, P2 medium with 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 g/L CaCO₃ treatments (fermentation time, 36 h). Lines 7 to 12 are *C. beijerinckii* 8052 cells from P2 medium, P2 medium with 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 g/L CaCO₃ treatments (fermentation time, 48 h). Line M is protein ladder standard.

Table 2: Amelioration of butanol toxicity to solventogenic *Clostridium* species (*C. acetobutylicum* 824, and *C. beijerinckii* 260) by CaCO₃. Both species had same growth characteristics during growth in media supplemented with different concentrations of butanol.

Treatments	Growth				
	0 g/L butanol	10 g/L butanol	12 g/L butanol	15 g/L butanol	20 g/L butanol
Control (P2 Medium)	+++++++	++++	+	-	-
P2 Medium + 4 g/L CaCO ₃	+++++++	+++++++	++++	+	-

+: growth; -: no growth; Number of + indicates intensity of growth.

Effect of butanol on growth of solventogenic *Clostridium* species

To evaluate performance of solventogenic *Clostridium* species when fermentation medium is supplemented with butanol, batch fermentations were conducted with P2 medium containing different concentrations of butanol (0-20 g/L) or P2 medium containing 4 g/L CaCO₃ and different concentrations of butanol (0-20 g/L). Solventogenic *Clostridium* species grew slowly in all P2 media containing 4 g/L CaCO₃ except in treatment containing 20 g/L butanol, unlike P2 medium with no CaCO₃ where *Clostridium* species barely grew in 12 g/L butanol treatment (Table 2). This demonstrates that the presence of CaCO₃ in the fermentation medium increased the threshold for butanol toxicity to *Clostridium* species. However, growth of solventogenic *Clostridium* species was prematurely terminated in treatments containing ≥ 15 g/L butanol following 8 h of post inoculation to the fermentation medium.

CONCLUSION

We have shown that CaCO₃ enhanced growth of solventogenic *Clostridium* species and butanol production. In addition, it appears CaCO₃ reduced the impact of butanol toxicity to solventogenic *Clostridium* species which lead to greater accumulation of butanol in the fermentation broth during ABE fermentation. Effect of CaCO₃ on solventogenic *Clostridium* species is non-selective in action and this finding may be applied to other microorganisms that undergo biphasic fermentation. Elevated protein expressions in solventogenic *Clostridium* species during fermentations in the presence of CaCO₃ are associated with enhanced growth and ABE production; the identity of these proteins and their mechanism of action remain to be deciphered.

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